

Studies on Soil Mycoflora of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Campus Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar

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ABSTRACT

Soil is a thin, natural layer on the Earth's surface composed of minerals, organic matter, water, air, and living organisms. Soils are very complex systems, with various components playing various roles mainly due to activity of soil organisms. Soil is a medium with solids, liquids and gases in which the mineral and organic particles form differently-sized aggregates that delimit. In order to assess soil conditions and promote plant growth, soil microflora is essential. Because they participate in a variety of biochemical transformation and mineralization processes in soils, microorganisms help to improve soil fertility and plant growth. Type of cultivation and crop management practices found to have greater influence on the activity of soil mycoflora. For this study we have selected the university campus sites for the soil mycoflora analysis. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar is located at latitude 19.902908° and longitude 75.310965° during the study 10 different sites of university campus were taken for study among these different 10 sites the total 67 fungal species were isolated from which 37 were seen dominantly in all localities were identified among them dominant sp. like *Penicillium*, *Alternaria* genera, *Aspergillus* genera were seen.

Keywords- Soil, Fungi, Soil mycoflora, Plant

INTRODUCTION

Soil is major components of the Earth's ecosystem. Soil is a product of several factors: the influence of climate, relief, organisms, and the soil's parent materials interacting over time (Gilluly et al. 1975). It continually undergoes development by way of numerous physical, chemical and biological processes, which include weathering with associated erosion. Given its complexity and strong internal connectedness, soil ecologists regard soil as an ecosystem (Ponge & Jean-francois 2015). Accordingly, soil is a three- state of solids, liquids, and gases (Mc Carthy, David f. 2014). Soil can effectively remove impurities, kill disease agents, and degrade contaminants, this latter property being called natural attenuation (Dominati et al. 2010). Soils maintain a net absorption of oxygen and methane and undergo a net release of carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide (Linn et al. 1984). Soils offer plants physical support, air, water, temperature moderation, nutrients, and protection from toxins

Composition of a silt loam soil by percent volume

(Gregory et al. 2013). Soils provide readily available nutrients to plants and animals by converting dead organic matter into various nutrient forms (Bot et al. 2005). A typical soil is about 50% solids (45% mineral and 5% organic matter), and 50% voids of which half is occupied by water and half by gas (Mc clellon & Tai 2022). The percent soil mineral and organic content is can be treated as a constant (in the short term), while the percent soil water and gas content is considered highly variable whereby a rise in one is simultaneously balanced by a reduction in the other (Arizonna Master & garden Manual 2017). The pore space allows for the infiltration and movement of air and water, both of which are critical for the life existing in soil (Vannier & Guy 1987). Compaction, a common problem and with soils, reduces this space, preventing air and water from reaching plant roots and soil organisms (Torbert et al. 1992).

The soil contains representatives of all groups of micro-organisms, fungi, bacteria, algae and viruses as well as the micro flora and fauna such as protozoa and nematodes. Soil microbes can have substantial effects on interactions among plants and the diversity and composition of plant communities (Wardle 2002). Several soil organisms offer benefits to crop growing in an ecosystem, but are not well understood. Soil microorganism, such as bacteria and fungi play an important role in soil fertility and in promoting plant health. Soil inhabits or initiates various species of microorganisms in nature. Researchers estimate the number at over a million species per gram of soil, although a later study suggests a maximum of just over 50,000 species per gram of soil (Ganset al.2005; Roeschet al.2007). Soil bacteria and fungi are the start of the soil food web that supports other organisms. Bacteria constitute the most abundant groups of microorganisms in soil and the fungal population of soils constitutes a very heterogenous group of

organisms. The bacterial genera *Nocardia*, *Streptomyces* and *Micro monospora* belong to order actinomycetes (aerobic and heterotrophic) are capable of degrading many complex organic substances and consequently play an important role in building soil fertility. The soil food web is interconnected matrix of invisible (fungi, bacteria, protozoa, nematodes) and visible (earthworms, beetles, arthropods) creatures that have a whole host of functions which creates a healthy ecosystem for plant growth. Various microorganisms were isolated from different soil samples collected. Thus, the population of total bacteria in rhizosphere was reported to be highest as compared as to non-rhizosphere. The majority of the bacteria were reported to be *Bacillus* and *Micrococcus* Species. The total fungal population densities were also decreased in non-rhizosphere while the highest fungal population was observed in rhizosphere. The majority of fungi were reported to be *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium species* and *Fusarium species*. A number of diazotrophs bacteria have abilities to fix Nitrogen, some strains may relieve deficiencies where there is an inadequate application of N fertilizers. Many heterotrophic bacteria live in the soil and fix significant levels of Nitrogen including *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum* and *Rhizobium*. N fixing microorganisms are globally noteworthy due to the fact as they provide only natural biological source of fixed N in the biosphere. The population count of *Azotobacter* was also more in rhizosphere than non-rhizosphere sites. (Harleen Kaur & Anshu Sibbal 2018).

The fungi are a group of organisms that lend themselves to sustainable use. Many fungal species can be isolated non-destructively from its native habitats and can grow in culture to be perpetuated and used indefinitely. Fungi are vital components of ecosystems, knowledge of the fungi as part of all-taxa biodiversity

inventory would add significantly to the success including the goal of demonstrating the economic value of biological resources. Fungi have important biogeochemical roles in the biosphere and are intimately involved in the cycling of elements and transformations of both organic and inorganic substrates (Gadd 2007). The diversity of soil microbes depends on the chemistry, texture and water holding capacity of soil: the success of fungi to reach and colonize a patch of soil is mainly due to their competitive saprophytic ability, expressed by fast mycelial growth and Spores production. Presence of an efficient and extensive system of powerful enzymes and tolerance to antibiotics (Wainwright, 1995). Fungi are ubiquitous and important because of their presence in all climates and on all substrates. Most of them can be easily cultured though some require special media to grow but the biotrophs fail to grow in axenic cultures. For proper growth and sporulation of a fungus specific requirements (nutrients, temperature, moisture, light, relative humidity etc.) of a fungus are to be fulfilled. (Amna Ali et. al., 2006). Fungi are an important component of the soil

mycoflora typically constituting more of the soil biomass than bacteria, depending on soil depth and nutrient conditions (Ainsworth & Bisby, 1995). Fungi play a significant role in the daily life of human beings besides their utilization in industry, agriculture, medicine, food industry, textiles, bioremediation, natural cycling, as bio fertilizers and many other ways. Fungal biotechnology has become an integral part of the human welfare (Manoharachary et al, 2005). This study aimed to soil mycoflora of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar campus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Location and site of Study area: -

The environment of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district is very much favorable for luxuriantly growth of fungi. Here some pathogenic and non-pathogenic soil fungi show diversity among them for this study different location in Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar.

Soil Collection Localities.

(Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar.)

Sr. No	Localities Name	Latitude/ Longitude	
1	V.C Home (Mango Garden)	Lat 19.896825 ⁰	Long 75.307202 ⁰
2	Boy's Hostel No-2 (Custard Apple)	Lat.19.907802 ⁰	Long 75.313992 ⁰
3	Botanical Garden No-3	Lat 19.903131 ⁰	Long 75.312759 ⁰
4	Chemistry Department	Lat 19.904633 ⁰	Long 75.310596 ⁰
5	History Museum	Lat 19.905077 ⁰	Long 75.32729 ⁰
6	Bhasha Bhavan (Mango Garden)	Lat 19.904896 ⁰	Long 75.315069 ⁰
7	Library	Lat 19.907801 ⁰	Long 75.314284 ⁰
8	Chemical Technology Department	Lat 19.903168 ⁰	Long 75.309487 ⁰
9	Tamarind and Amla Garden	Lat 19.912088 ⁰	Long 75.313459 ⁰
10	Custard Garden	Lat 19.895086 ⁰	Long 75.304302 ⁰

Collection of Soil sample: -

The Soil sample was collected from different localities such as Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar. The soil sample were collected the Month of December 2021 with regular intervals. Plant root area to the death 15cm with the help of sterilized cork borer. From each selected location conventional and organic fields, the rhizosphere soils from the root zones of the plant were collected randomly and mixed together to obtain a homogenous soil sample. Soil collected in sterilized zip lock polythene bag. Each polythene bag was labeled properly by indicating the site of collection, date and time collected and then sample were taken to the laboratory.

PLATE - 1

Isolation of soil mycoflora by serial dilution

Method:

For studying the fungi present in soil the dilution plate method developed by (Waksman, 1927) used for isolation of rhizosphere mycoflora of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar. For the isolation of fungi serial dilution factor 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , and 10^{-3} used.

Selection of Media for Isolation: -

During investigation usually Rose Bengal Agar (RBA) and Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium were used for the isolation and maintenance of pure cultures.

Slide Preparation:

A slide was taken and cleans with alcohol and a drop of lactophenol cotton blue was added on slide and the culture from the edge of the colony was placed over if followed by a cover slip. Then the fungal structure was examined under the microscope.

Microscopic Identification:

After the growth of fungus on Petri plates. The macroscopic observations were done by external feature, texture, colony color, growth rate and microscopic characteristics are the arrangement of spore. The identification of fungi was done by using the various research paper, monograph and other literature such as manual of soil fungi, Illustration of Fungi, Handbook of soil fungi, Fuskey Fusarium interactive key an illustrated manual of fungi.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

During the isolation major 67 fungi found from the different localities of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Campus including V.C. Home (Mango Garden), Boy's Hostel No.-2 (Custard apple), Botanical Garden No. 3, Chemistry Department, History Museum, Bhasha Bhavan (Mango Garden), Library, Chemical Technology Department, Tamarind and Amla Garden, Custard Garden these Localities were selected.

Table 1: Soil Mycoflora of Different Localities in Dr. BAMU Campus At Winter season

Sr No.	Fungus Name	localities									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01	<i>Alternaria Spp.</i>	+		+			+				
02	<i>Aspergillus cremeus</i>			+							
03	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>						+				
04	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>				+						+
05	<i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>			+							
06	<i>Aspergillus japonicus</i>								+		+
07	<i>Aspergillus kanagwaensis</i>	+		+				+			
08	<i>Aspergillus malbranchea</i>			+							
09	<i>Aspergillus nidulence</i>									+	
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		+	+	+	+		+	+		
11	<i>Aspergillus Parasiticus</i>				+					+	
12	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	+						+			
13	<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>			+		+					
14	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>										
15	<i>Aspergillus violaceofuscus</i>						+		+		
16	<i>Aspergillus wentii</i>	+	+								
17	<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>			+		+			+	+	
18	<i>Cladosporium montecillanum</i>		+							+	
19	<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i>			+		+	+			+	
20	<i>Colletotrichum Spp.</i>										+
21	<i>Fusarium proliferatum</i>		+		+	+					
22	<i>Fusarium sporotrichioides</i>			+	+				+		
23	<i>Monodicytes</i>	+									+
24	<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	+		+			+	+	+		
25	<i>Penicillium talaromyces</i>				+	+					+
26	<i>Penicillium viridicatum</i>		+		+			+			
27	<i>Rhizopous microspores</i>	+	+					+			
28	<i>Rhizopous stolonifer</i>			+						+	
29	<i>Staphyotrichum</i>		+								+
30	<i>Tolura herbarum</i>		+			+					
31	<i>Trichocladium asperum</i>	+			+			+			
32	<i>Trichoderma Spp.</i>			+							
33	<i>Unknown1</i>		+						+		
34	<i>Unknown2</i>										+

Table 2: Soil Mycoflora of Different Localities in Dr. BAMU Campus At Summer Season.

Sr No.	Fungus Name	localities									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01	<i>Alternariya Spp.</i>	+				+			+		
02	<i>Aspergillus cremeus</i>										+
03	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	+		+			+				+
04	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	+			+						+
05	<i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>			+							
06	<i>Aspergillus joponicus</i>						+		+		+
07	<i>Aspergillus kanagwaensis</i>		+					+			
08	<i>Aspergillus malbranchea</i>		+	+						+	+
09	<i>Aspergillus nidulence</i>	+									
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		+	+	+	+		+	+		
11	<i>Aspergillus Parasiticus</i>	+		+	+				+	+	+
12	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>		+				+			+	+
13	<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>		+			+					+
14	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>			+						+	+
15	<i>Aspergillus violaceofuscus</i>								+		+
16	<i>Aspergillus wenti</i>	+			+			+			
17	<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>			+			+		+	+	
18	<i>Cladosporium montecillanum</i>		+		+	+				+	+
19	<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i>				+	+		+		+	+
20	<i>Colletotrichum Spp.</i>			+							+
21	<i>Fusarium proliferatum</i>		+		+	+		+			
22	<i>Fusarium sporotrichioides</i>	+			+						
23	<i>Monodicytes</i>	+	+	+				+			
24	<i>Penecillium viridicatum</i>			+	+		+				+
25	<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	+	+	+						+	+
26	<i>Penicillium talaromyces</i>				+				+		
27	<i>Rhizopous microspores</i>	+	+					+	+		
28	<i>Rhizopous stolonifer</i>			+					+		
29	<i>Staphytotrichum</i>		+								
30	<i>Tolura herbarum</i>		+				+				
31	<i>Trichocladium asperum</i>			+	+						
32	<i>Trichoderma Spp.</i>		+			+		+		+	+
33	<i>Unknown</i>	+	+								

Table 3: Soil Mycoflora of Different Localities in Dr. BAMU Campus At Rainy Season.

Sr No.	Fungus Name	localities									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01	<i>Alternaria Spp.</i>								+	+	+
02	<i>Alternaria Spp 1</i>		+								
03	<i>Aspergillus cremeus</i>			+	+			+			
04	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	+					+				
05	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>			+	+				+		+
06	<i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>		+	+						+	+
07	<i>Aspergillus japonicus</i>					+		+	+		
08	<i>Aspergillus kanagwaensis</i>			+				+			+
09	<i>Aspergillus malbranchea</i>	+		+	+				+		
10	<i>Aspergillus nidulence</i>	+					+		+		+
11	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		+	+	+	+		+	+		
12	<i>Aspergillus Parasiticus</i>					+		+		+	+
13	<i>Aspergillus Spp 1</i>		+								
14	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	+		+							
15	<i>Aspergillus ustus</i>				+	+		+			
16	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>		+				+		+	+	+
17	<i>Aspergillus violaceofuscus</i>					+			+		
18	<i>Aspergillus wenti</i>	+	+		+						
19	<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>		+	+			+	+	+	+	+
20	<i>Cladosporium montecillanum</i>			+				+		+	
21	<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i>					+	+	+		+	+
22	<i>Colletotrichum Spp.</i>		+								
23	<i>Fusarium proliferatum</i>				+	+					
24	<i>Fusarium sporotrichioides</i>	+			+	+			+	+	
25	<i>Monodicytes</i>	+		+							
26	<i>Penicillium mviridicatum</i>		+		+	+			+		+
27	<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	+	+				+	+			
28	<i>Penicillium Spp 1</i>	+	+		+		+		+	+	+
29	<i>Penicillium talaromyces</i>				+						
30	<i>Rhizopus microspores</i>	+						+			
31	<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>			+	+			+			
32	<i>Rhizopus Spp 1</i>										
33	<i>Staphyotrichum</i>		+				+				
34	<i>Tolura herbarum</i>		+			+		+		+	
35	<i>Trichocladium sperum</i>				+				+		
36	<i>Unknown 1</i>				+		+	+	+		
37	<i>Trichoderma</i>		+		+		+		+		

PLATE - 2

ISOLATION OF SOIL MYCOFLORA ON PDA MEDIA

PLATE - 3

ISOLATION OF SOIL MYCOFLORA ON RBA MEDIA

PLATE - 4

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

PLATE - 5

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

PLATE - 6

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

PLATE - 7

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

PLATE - 8

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

PLATE - 9

Pure culture and microphotograph of fungi

CONCLUSION

During the isolation major 67 fungi found from the different localities were selected. It was clear from the table then Winter season *Aspergillus* genera show dominant at every locality, followed by *Penicillium* genera. Among the diversity of fungi where seen *Alternaria* was found only at rainy season. In summer season from locality no 10, the *Aspergillus* genera found to be dominant compare to other fungal genera. In Rainy season most of the fungal genera found in locality no 4, such as *Aspergillus Species*, *Penicillium Species*, *Cladosporium Species*, *Fusarium Species*, *Rhizopus Species*, *Trichoderma Species*, etc. Among then the *Aspergillus* genera where dominant found at every locality as well as The *Penicillium* variety species were seen dominant at every locality, or selected soils sample. Among the species from diversity of fungus species at localities as well as different season condition. It is interesting observation was observed during the 3 season localities rainy season fungal load was found more as compare followed by winter season, and in summer season as occurs was depleted dominantly research.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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